

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

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Annotation: France and Germany occupy one of the leading positions within the economically developed countries of the world. Its educational system is also ancient and has a rich history. The main goal of French education is to ensure the comprehensive maturation of a person, prepare him for independent activities, ensure the perfection of market relations, prepare him for independent activities, teach students to entrepreneurship, business and factor in the conditions of market attitudes, and direct him to a specific profession. Reading in elementary grades is divided into morning and afternoon.

Keywords: World Education, higher Education, education system.

In France, primary education schools attract children between the ages of 6 and 11. Special importance is also attached to the education of elegance in French schools. Such education consists of three procedures: music, Fine Arts and sports. Higher education professional education in France was decided over the next 20 years. In France, there are higher technological institutes that provide higher education and specialization. French education systems do not provide for after-school and extracurricular institutions. However, there are different circles in schools and lyceums. For students, various sports sections are organized on trips, competitions in the educational institution itself. French youth, foreign nationals who come to France for Education receive higher education in the following knowledge institutions:

Universities;

Higher technology schools;

Higher engineering schools;

Higher schools of architecture;

Higher commercial schools;

Higher School of political science;

Higher pedagogical and philological knowledge;

Higher medical educational institutions;

Higher schools of Fine Arts;

Impartial Education [qualification]

Higher education universities provide their students with knowledge in three cycles. The first cycle ends with a higher education in a general or any technical or scientific field, and the study takes two years. Students complete it with metrized, master's degrees. The third cycle takes one to two years of study.

diploma about the deepening study of any subject (one year);

diploma on specialized higher education (one year);

third cycle doctoral dissertation (one, two years);

State doctoral dissertation-it is possible to study any area perfectly and get documents such as writing a dissertation.

In France, there are higher technological institutes that provide higher education and specialization. They are usually specialized in industrial, domestic services, Informatics specialties. The duration of study is 2 years, classes are 30-35 hours per week. During the study, an 8-week production practice is also envisaged.

More than a thousand such institutes operate in France, preparing specialists in agricultural production, art, Informatics, administrative management, accounting, applied arts. Access to such institutes is carried out without an examination.

It should be noted that the path to Germany's market economy will look like in our Republic. The education system also has its own stage of development in Germany,

which is among the strongest countries within the economically developed countries of the world, which contribute significantly to the social, economic, political development of the world. The preschool system is an important stage in the German education system. It has more than a hundred years of history.

Compulsory education is for children between the ages of 6 and 18. Teaching is free in public schools, students are provided free of charge with textbooks and teaching aids.

How is school education built in Germany and in what order are teaching activities organized? After a full four years of Primary School, students continue their education in line-based schools. The basic school program is analyzed year by year. In Germany, the opportunity to acquire knowledge was created for adults who were not able to get an education in a timely manner. In the evening gymnasium, workers in industries such as industry, agriculture submit an examination to obtain an attestation of maturity after passing the training blind for 3-6 years. Because the vocational education system in Germany is of great importance, the demand for highly skilled workers in Germany is high.

Another of the peculiarities of the German educational system is that vocational diplomas do not give the right to enter higher educational institutions and study. Admission is based on a document on school education without registration. The institution of higher education is headed by the rector in the state or the president elected for several years. The main focus of research in higher educational institutions is fundamental applied research, which is closely assisted by other scientific research institutes, industrial laboratories .

Higher education institutions, which are private except those belonging to the church and Bundeswehr, are under the administration of the provinces. They are administered by the Federation of Higher Education on behalf of the head of lands. The Federation regulates general principles relating to the higher education system. In

particular, the Federation takes over the construction of a higher educational institution and the provision of funds for part of the research at the higher educational institution.

The Higher School has the right to self-government. They accept their charters within the framework of the law.

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